

AEROSPACE MATERIALS AND STRUCTURAL RESEARCH INTO THE NEXT MILLENNIUM

Jim C. I. Chang

*Aerospace and Materials Sciences Directorate
Air Force Office of Scientific Research
110 Duncan Avenue, Suite B115
Bolling AFB DC 20332-8050
USA*

SUMMARY: The aerospace materials and structures community has made major advances during the past fifty years. Specifically, the development of composite materials has offered design engineers the opportunities for designing high performance aerospace systems which otherwise would be impossible to attain. Today, as we approach the beginning of the next millennium, it is both academically satisfying and practically beneficial to examine where we have been and to speculate where we will be. An assessment on the state-of-the-art of the advanced composites as well as their limitations and investment strategy is presented here. All materials including, metal and polymeric, metal, and ceramic composites are discussed. The impact and challenge presented to the materials technology developers from advancement in computing and manufacturing, and from paradigm shift in structural designs philosophy such as multi-functional smart structures are also addressed. Finally, research opportunities and the next frontier of materials research are discussed.

KEYWORDS: composites, structures, solid mechanics, computer simulation materials design, smart structures, multi-functional structures, manufacturing and processing.

INTRODUCTION

The opportunity and challenge to the materials scientists in the next century are (1) to design materials for a purpose; not to design the best materials possible, and (2) to predict materials performance; not to characterize as is materials. To meet this challenge, an integrated-proactive materials research approach must be adopted. The structural material core technology (Fig. 1) concept used by the US Air Force Office of Scientific Research (AFOSR) is an excellent example of the proactive approach for materials program planning and development. The multi-disciplinary integration approach (Fig. 2) is the key for assuring the development of quality and low cost materials.

Composite materials have been used since the dawn of the civilization. Early Egyptians knew to mix straw and earth to increase toughness, and Chinese used cooked rice mixture to cement earth blocks. However, the major advancement to the understanding and utilization of composite materials has come about only within the last fifty years. For any material or material systems, the most simplified design parameters are strength and toughness. The figure-of-merit of different material systems has been discussed in Ref. 1, and they are illustrated in Figs. 3 & 4. Among all composites, polymeric composites have made the most

impact where military and civilian aircraft made of this type of composite have been built and are being flown all around the world. However, as they are being used, the knowledge based on the polymeric composites durability from usage and from environmental degradation is

found lacking. Therefore, basic research in this area is being revamped. On the other hand, because of the need of high performance air vehicles, composites having different attributes have also been extensively investigated and developed. Metal matrix composites and ceramic matrix composites are the commonly known composites where stiffness, strength and elevated temperature capability are the main development goals. Today, the material technology development process has reached a cross road where the feasibility of certain class of composites to attain the postulate performance goals must be realistically assessed. Specifically, it must be assessed against the practicality and feasibility of these materials being actually used for engineering applications. For example, can technical breakthrough realize the desire of using bulk ceramic composites for turbine engine rotating components applications? Or should other ceramic technologies, such as coatings, that offer less performance improvement but have a real possibility of success be the areas of emphasis? In the mean time, have we reached the new frontier where new advancements such as, nanotechnology and computationally materials modeling offer the scientists with the tools to “design” materials? More importantly, the materials research effort must also be compatible with the aerospace vehicle design paradigm shift. The future aerospace structures are not bonded by the conventional aerodynamically-based designed principles, i.e., tailless aircraft and smart multi-functional airframe. In this case, structural and functional composites could be one single identity, and metal and non-metal are no longer separate classes of materials but hybrid composites instead.

METAL AND METALLIC COMPOSITES

Metal is the basic material that has been used extensively for centuries. Therefore, the utilization and development of non-metal composites must be examined in light of the advancement made by the metal community. From the aerospace materials point of view, the trend toward higher temperature materials has steered the emphasis to composites. In fact, this has been precisely the trend for materials development in the last thirty years. However, the advancement made in experimental capability, processing and fundamental understanding has pushed metal into a new frontier - higher strength/stiffness and elevated temperature capability. This latest development has given the nonmetallic-composites, especially carbon-carbon and ceramic composite materials a run for its money.

For high temperature applications, metals and metal composites have definitively proven their worth beyond conventional wisdom. Fig. 5 illustrates the metal and metal composites lifecycle and investment strategy used by the AFOSR metals program. Monolithic metals, Ti, Al and Ni have reached technology maturity where only limited investment is need for specific applications. High cycle fatigue of Ti is an example. The next category, such as TiAl and NiAl, is near the tail end of basic research but substantial investment is still needed to address unique issues that prevent these materials potential being realized. Fracture toughness of intermetallics is such an example. In fact, intermetallics are strong competitors to composites for turbine fan blade applications. The majority of innovative basic research effort in metals and metal composite is in elevated temperature applications. Both Nb-Si and Mo-Si-B, have high creep resistance properties and oxidation resistance characteristics (Figs. 6 & 7), and they are true contenders to ceramic composites for high temperature applications

(Refs. 2 & 3). Fundamentally, Nb-Si is relatively stable up to 1670⁰C and is 80% lighter than Ni-superalloys. Because of these characteristics and the advancement made to date, the possibility of using these metallic systems for engine applications is much higher than that of the ceramic composites. Some other advanced metallic systems are distinguished by their unique features such as metallic glass (Ref. 4), or by their physical dimensions such as microlaminates or nanomaterials. Metallic glass (Fig. 8) is an alloy-glass systems where metal alloying and unique processing provide materials with exceptional strength and ductility. Nano-and micro-laminated materials are hybrid materials that are tailored for specific thermal or mechanical properties, and are far better than most of the single phase material or macro-multi-phases composites can ever attain (Figs. 9, 10 & 11). All these achievements are possible because advancement made in fundamental understanding and in newly developed processing techniques (Refs. 5 & 6). Nevertheless, the frontier has just been opened, new opportunity and challenge are plenty and substantive advancement in metal and metal composites is expected.

Metal Matrix Composites (MMC) have their unique characteristics that lend themselves for specific applications. These characteristics include high stiffness, low coefficient of thermal expansion and high thermal conductivity. For space structures, all these properties are desirable and essential for vibration control and for minimizing the effects from cyclic thermal environment in space. Additionally, the dimensional stability and low outgassing requirement of most space platforms makes MMC ideal materials. However, after more than three decades of research and development, the cost of making MMC and the difficulty of making quality components have prevented this materials being used extensively. At the same time, advancement of other type of materials have provided solutions to space structural applications which would otherwise depend solely on MMC.

There are still many research issues in MMC to be pursued. When answers to these issues are found, MMC may make a come back and become the materials of choice again. Issues related to quality and low cost production are the key areas that require research attention. Additionally, there are many other research issues that are applications specific. For example, the making and qualifying of MMC dimensional stability is still a challenge to space applications. Because of the high temperature infiltration and solidification processes that the matrix material experiences, substantial thermal induced residual stresses are locked in the processed composites. This process induced thermal stress is the major contributor to the MMC hysteresis loop behavior which leads to unstable structural geometry from thermal cycling during service. Innovative processing techniques to alleviate this problem, and new and rigorous thermal mechanical theory which takes care of nonlinear interaction between the thermal and mechanical stresses is needed to predict this behavior. The latter case can not bear fruit from the conventional linear thermo-elastic or thermo-plastic theory and it must start from fundamental thermodynamics.

POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

Performance, processing and manufacturing, and maintainability are the three major considerations for using any material. Because of its relative maturity, the research needs of polymeric composite are easier to define in this context. Polymeric composites become viable engineering materials following twenty years of research and development effort. As in the case of any new materials development effort, the major emphasis has been on performance. In terms of processing and manufacturing, most effort has been focused on

property improvement, and cost reduction has not been a driver. One of few processing and fabrication success stories is Resin Transfer Molding (RTM). For this reason, the usage of polymeric composites are still rather limited. Therefore, low cost processing and manufacturing requires attention.

As far as maintainability is concerned, our knowledge is very limited. Because polymeric composites have been widely used for aircraft, missile and space systems for some time, performance degradation from service environment exposure has become a major issue to the maintenance and operation of these systems. This is one of the important areas where basic research as well as engineering development effort is needed. The types of degradation we are talking about here are thermo-oxidation degradation and solvent/moisture induced degradation. In this case, the traditional approach of looking at the macroscopic scale is no longer sufficient. Specifically, thermo-oxidative degradation is a chemistry process; solvent/moisture induced degradation is a combined chemical and physical process. Therefore, in order to scientifically determine the so called "damage initiation", the physics and chemistry of the polymer molecular architecture change from processing to service must be understood. Fig. 12 illustrates one of the AFOSR polymeric composites program thrusts on polymeric composites degradation where damage initiation mechanisms are addressed in a comprehensive manner. The fundamental effects addressed include chemical structures effects and chemical degradation, network effects, mechanical stress effects, and thermoplastic processing. Each effect is a complicated one. For example, the moisture uptake depends on the time, temperature and history, and is dictated by the physical states of the polymer. One of the physical states that plays a major role to the process of degradation is porosity. There are open porosity and close porosity which dictate the probability of moisture infiltration and retention. The definition and the measurement of these types of porosity and its effects on moisture retention is at the basic research stage. Figs. 13 and 14 illustrate a technique of using positron for measuring porosity and the hole effects on controlling moisture diffusion (Ref. 7). By breaking up the porosity into static and dynamic holes, the preliminary data suggested that only the static holes control the moisture diffusion below the glass transition temperature. The stress effect on sorption is illustrated in Fig. 15. This formulation was developed by Treloar for rubber (Ref. 8), which is different from conventional polymer. However, from the fundamental chemistry point of view, this is a start.

Lastly, the issue of Non-Destructive Evaluation of polymeric composites has been addressed by engineers as measuring structural integrity or mechanical separation of materials, i.e., delamination and other damage from fabrication and usage. However, the new frontier is to be able to interrogate the chemical state of the polymer non-destructively, and to scientifically relate these measurements to the mechanical and chemically conditions of the materials. With this capability, the material engineers will be able to see and to predict actual material separation before it happens. This knowledge is important to the use of composites itself as well as to the development and usage of adhesive bonding technique which is extremely desirable but not widely used due to its low reliability.

CERAMICS AND CERAMIC COMPOSITES

Ceramic materials offer elevated temperature capability but are weak from fracture. For this reason, for more than thirty years, the ceramists have been trying to realize the high temperature capability and to improve materials toughness. Both transformation toughening and second phase reinforced ceramics have been the center of most research effort.

Unfortunately, despite substantial investment and research on different fiber reinforced ceramics, the so called “toughened ceramic composite” remains a concept. The toughness derives from the added reinforcement is no where near to be useful. Additionally, the lack of solution to alleviate oxidation problem has prevented the elevated temperature capability being realized. Investment and effort in oxidation resistance coatings for ceramic composites has been substantial but has not produced useful product. At the same time, other newly developed materials, such as strong and elevated temperature metallic systems have practically taken the steam of the ceramic composites development momentum. In fact, it is the critical time to the ceramic composite research community, and a critical self evaluation is needed in order to maintain this momentum. The reality is that without realistic probability of these materials being used in the reasonable future, and under the present fiscal environment, the resources sponsors in the government and industry can not and will not sustain the amount of investment in ceramics and ceramic composites research as they have been doing in the past twenty years. This statement does not imply that no research should be done in ceramic composites. Basic research should be focused to looking at the critical issues rather than making different kinds of composite materials. In this case, the investment will be smaller, selective and focused. For example, to use these materials for elevated temperature applications, research on ceramic composites should be focused on elevated temperature properties not on extensive analysis and testing at room temperatures. The AFOSR ceramics and ceramics composites program is a program that takes on this balanced approach.

Bulk ceramics can sustain severe compressive loads without failure. For this reason, it is ideal to use monolithic ceramics for this type of applications, such as ceramic bearings. Ceramic bearings are superior to metal bearings for their high abrasive resistance, elevated temperature capability and requiring no lubricant. Research on processing, particle size effects and failure under compression for achieving surface strengthening and toughening of bulk ceramics are all excellent issues. Fig. 16 (Ref. 9) illustrates the relationship between the particle size and the failure modes of Silicon Nitride from indentation tests. With this type of preliminary information, ceramic bearings have been fabricated and tested in the space shuttle and aircraft auxiliary power units. However, these trial runs have also revealed that the integrity of these bearings are very sensitive to contamination. Therefore, in order to use ceramic bearings, materials processing and their response to chemical/thermal/mechanical environment must be fully understood.

Other ceramics and ceramic composites applications that will result in huge cost savings are ceramic coatings - Thermal Barrier Coating (TBC) and abrasion resistance coating. TBC on engine components leads to huge saving from increased efficiency as the operating temperature is increased. Abrasion resistance coating can reduce wear loss and increase component life and operation efficiency from friction reduction. The research issues on TBC are oxidation and structural integrity of the coatings. The focus must be on the coating system which contains substrate, transition coating and the TBC itself. It is a combined chemical, thermal and mechanical issue plus materials development effort. Fig. 17 illustrates the figure-of-merit for designing a TBC for purely thermal mechanical response (Ref. 1). One should realize that the integrity of a TBC is controlled by adhesion, stress, deformation and failure modes, and these variables are nonlinearly coupled with oxidation degradation of the coating system. TBC is a hot issue in the engine community because it offers the real possibility of substantial savings for operating a engine. However, many unanswered technology questions have prevented TBC from being used to its maximum potential.

Coating for friction reduction is a different matter whereas the hardness is the figure-of-merit. In this case, diamond coating is the most desirable kind. However, basic research to date has demonstrated that ceramic coatings having near the diamond hardness could be fabricated. For example, it has been known that the theoretical hardness of CN_x (Ref. 10) could be comparable to that of the diamond. The issue is to know enough fundamentals and to process it into crystalline structures rather than in the amorphous forms which only have about one third of the hardness (around 30 GPa) as that of the diamond. A structural template approach (Fig. 18) which grows CN_x coating pseudomorphically on a template has been developed (Ref. 10). The function of the template is to provide a method to maintain minimum interfacial energy between the coating and the template materials. For CN_x coatings, TiN, ZrN and HfN are candidate template materials. With this arrangement and properly chosen controlled wavelength, typical PVD processed coating having a hardness around 60 GPa have been produced (Fig. 19).

The knowledge base on how to make toughened ceramic composites for elevated applications is much less matured. In terms of fundamental properties, two most important and also most difficult problems are oxidation and toughness. There is no good solution to prevent oxidation and no viable means to achieve toughness from second or third phase reinforcement. In terms of applications, fabricate quality components at low cost is still a long way off.

To date, the community does not have enough understanding to make a toughened ceramic composite. Therefore, it is a mistake for anyone even to try to do so. Specifically, the composite toughness is highly depended on the as processed interface and its reaction to load transfer, and on the properties of the fibers and the matrix especially their chemical and thermal stability at elevated temperatures. However, from the engineering point of view, one can divide the research focus into near term and far term expectations. Short of a set of answers, one can still expect to develop ceramic composites for near term non-load bearing high temperature applications, such as nozzle liners, or for one time, short duration applications, such as a missile engines. For example, weaved ceramic composites having sufficient transverse strength can be used provided that the oxidation degradation is designed into the components. In this case, good oxide fibers and oxide matrix are possible candidate materials for fabrication. As far as using ceramic composites for rotating components in a jet engine, we will need better fundamental knowledge. Therefore, instead of making ceramic composites, one should attack these fundamental issues with vigor. Specifically, the best pure and high quality fibers must be developed and fabricated to alleviate oxidation problems. For long duration applications, such as jet engines, no matter what type of coating is being developed and used, cracks will develop and oxygen will get through to the fibers. In this case, none of the available oxide-fibers available fits the definition. However, some major advancements have been made in the laboratory (Ref. 11). The pure SN fibers, UG-HM, have been fabricated and tested along with standard Hi-Nicalon and Nicalon fibers for oxidation resistance and for mechanical load-carrying capability with success (Fig. 20). Let us turn our attention to the interface. To achieve the fiber debonding for toughened composites, proper chemical and mechanical characteristics must be incorporated into the interface. Specifically, one must be able to fabricate the interface that is stable chemically at elevated temperatures and will debond upon load impinging by an on-coming crack. W. P. Kriven has developed a laser deposition technique for coating the fibers to achieve this goal. Fig. 21 depicts the successful interface which is stable at a temperature up to 1450⁰C and can debond upon applied stress. (Ref. 12)

Lastly is the processing issue. The ceramics and ceramic composites processing techniques available to date can not guarantee quality and are very expensive as well. Novel methods must be developed to translate laboratory proven materials for mass production. There are a lot of on-going effort but very few lend themselves to low cost and quality processing. One method offers potential and fits under the meaning of innovation. Prof. K Sandhage and H Fraser (Ref. 11) looked at the causes of the problems associated with ceramics and ceramic composites processing - shrinkage, porosity and machining. To alleviate the shrinkage problem, they choose to add a small amount of Alkaline Earth materials, which shrink upon sintering because their oxides have smaller molar volume than the metal itself, into the ceramic precursor. In doing so, the total volume change of the mixed precursor could be close to zero. Because there is no volume change from sintering, there is no shrinkage or cracking. Additionally, the precursor is suitable to be processed the same way as those used in the powder metallurgy processing. Specifically, one can use casting or rolling processes to make the composites into final component shapes. No machining is required because this process produces no change in dimension from sintering.

SOLID MECHANICS, SMART STRUCTURES AND INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

As stated at the beginning of this paper, the challenge for materials scientists is to design a material for a purpose and to predict its behavior before this material is fabricated. For this reason, correct solid mechanics principles that connect the micro- and macro- behavior must be developed and used. Figs 22 & 23 are such examples (Ref. 13). Knowing the properties of each of the constituents of a composite, one can design composite materials and control different failure modes. However, as the materials become more complicated, the mechanics principles that have been developed and used for isotropic and homogeneous materials are no longer valid. Specifically, for any composite material, deformation and damage are nonlinearly coupled, and damage initiates only at a fraction of the ultimate load. There is no distinct “yielding” or “proportional limit” where linear deformation does not come about from material damage. For this reason, a set of new mechanics principles for composite materials must be developed to account for these behaviors. Fig. 24 depicts the processes and the needs. Good results have been generated and one of such examples is illustrated in Fig. 25 - failure criteria for various materials categories (Ref. 14).

The ultimate objective of material development is to make components and systems. The only way to achieve this goal is through close collaboration among the mechanics researchers, materials specialists and structural engineers. Only the structural engineers can define the needs. With the accurate mechanics principles, the mechanics researchers can translate these needs into material properties requirements and also use them for performance prediction. These requirements in turn become materials development goals. For this reason, the paradigm shift in structural design will have a major impact to materials research in the next century. The next generation of aerospace structures will be multi-functional i.e. designed for load-carrying, communication as well as for other smart performance such as health monitoring and self healing. These structural systems have been loosely called “smart structures” or “adaptive structures”. The relevant disciplines to achieve the “smartness” are materials, structures, aerodynamics, electronics, electromagnetic, sensors and actuators, and control. Smart structure is an integrated sensors/actuators and load-carrying system having embedded sensors and actuators that can be used for health monitoring, control feedback, communication (antenna), performance improvement and other functions. Because a smart

structure is to perform many different functions (mechanical, electrical and optical), the critical research topics are to understand and to take advantage of the interrelatedness among these disciplines. For example, one form of the smart structures is an integrated airframe and antenna system that can carry load, monitor materials integrity, communicate in the electromagnetic wave spectrum, and also must have low signature characteristics and perform well aerodynamically (good flying quality). The only means to achieve this goal is to do discipline research and carefully explore the interrelatedness issues among all these disciplines. Among the selective topics being addressed are: deformable airframe for low signature systems and tailless aircraft, distributed sensors and actuators systems, neural net coupled control, optimal energy allocation for control architectural design, MicroElectroMechanical Systems (MEMS) and host-sensor interactions. MEMS are miniature electrical, mechanical and possibly optical systems at micron-size which can be used as distributed sensors and actuators. The spin off potential of MEMS is unlimited. In addition to use them for system control purposes, they can revolutionize manufacturing, processing, robotics, space applications, etc.

A FEW WORDS ABOUT THE FUTURE

In addition to the integrated-collaborated effort, future materials research will be greatly enhanced by the new developments in instrumentation and in computing power. Today, material researchers have already demonstrated that nano-layer materials at micron level made from different materials groups, metal, polymer and ceramics, can be fabricated. The uniqueness of this development is that the traditional division lines among different materials groups have been broken for the purpose of picking the best material system to do a special job. On the computational power side, one may speculate that the future materials could be designed from atomic structures level and up. Fig. 26 illustrates a calculated electron energy density distribution of TiAl materials having different alloy composition. It is a first principle calculation (Ref. 15), but it is still far off from this technique being used to design a real material. However, the electron density distributions do provide some insight as to the relative property change from introducing different alloy into the material systems

REFERENCES

1. A. G. Evans, Implementation Challenges for High Temperature Composites, Mech-283 Harvard University Publications, 1996
2. D. M. Dimiduk, P.R. Subramanian, and M. G. Mendiratta, Acta. Metall. Sinica, 8 (1995) pp. 519-30.
3. P. R. Subramanian, M. G. Mendiratta, and D. M. Dimiduk, JOM, 48(1), (1996), pp. 33-38
4. W. L. Johnson, Current Opinion in Solid State and Materials Science, 1, 383 (1996)
5. J. J. Lewandowski, C. H. Ward, M. R. Jackson, and W. H. Hunt, Jr., eds., Layered Materials for Structural Applications, Vol. 434, Pittsburgh, PA: Materials Research Society, 1996.

6. R. G. Rowe, D. W. Skelly, M. R. Jackson, M. Larson, and D. Wachapelle, Layered Materials for Structural Applications, Vol. 434, J. J. Lewandowski, C. H. Ward, M. R. Jackson, and W. H. Hunt Jr., Eds., Pittsburgh, PA: Materials Research Society, 1996, pp. 3-13.
7. H. Hristov, B. Bolan, A. F. Yee, L. Xie, and D. Gidley, "Measurement of Hole Volume in Amorphous Polymers Using Positron Spectroscopy", *Macromolecules*, 1996, V. 29, p. 8507.
8. C. J. Wolf and H. Fu, "Stress Enhanced Transport of Toluene in Poly Aryl Ether Ether Ketone (PEEK), *J. Polym. Sci. (Phys. Ed.)* 34, 75-82 (1996).
9. S. K. Lee, S. Wuttiphan and B. R. Lawn, "Role of Microstructure in Hertzian Contact Damage in Silicon Nitride: I. Mechanical Characterization," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* (In press).
10. D. D. Li, M. S. Wang, Y. W. Chung, S. C. cheng, X. Chu, X. W. Lin and W. D. Sproul, "Structure & Hardness Studies of CN_x/TiN Nanocomposite Coatings." *J. of Appl. Phys. Letters*
11. M. D. Sacks, A. A. Morrone, G. W. Scheiffele, and M. Saleem, "Characterization of Polymer-Derived Silicon Carbide Fibers with Low Oxygen Content, Near-Stoichiometric Composition, and Improved Thermomechanical Stability," *Ceram. Eng. Sci. Proc.*, 16 [4] 25--35 (1995).
12. Chao M. Huang, Y. Xu, Fulin Xiong, A. Zangvil, and W. Kriven, "Layer Ablated Coatings on Ceramic Fibers for Ceramic Matrix Composites," *Materials Science & Engineering Journal*, March 1995.
13. N. Pogano, *Journal of Composites, Part B*, In press, 97
14. N. Chien, T. Honein, and G. Herrmann, "Conservation Laws for Non-Homogeneous Mindlin Plates," *Int. J. Engineering Science*, 1994.
15. Y. Song, S. P. Tang, J. H. Yu, O. N. Hryasox, A. J. Freeman, C. Woodward, and D. M. Dimiduk, *Phil. Mag. B*, 70, (r), (1994), pp. 987-1002.

Fig. 1 AFOSR Structural Materials Core Technology

Fig. 2 Integrated-Proactive Materials Research

Fig. 3(a) Figure-of-Merit for Material Modulus/Density

Fig. 3(b) Figure-of-Merit for Material Modulus/Density

Fig. 4 Figure-of-Merit for Materials Toughness

Fig. 5 AFOSR Metals/Metals Composites Research Strategy

Fig. 6 Recession Rate of Various Metals/Metal Composites

- Region of relative stability to 1670°C
– Potential for use to 1300°C or higher
- Reinforcing Nb₅Si₃ very creep resistant
- Nb has low solubility for Si, but is readily alloyed with other elements
- 80% the density of Ni-superalloys

Fig. 7 Figure-of-Merit of Nb-Si

Fig. 8(a) Specific Strength of Different Metal Systems

Fig. 8(b) Elongation of Metallic Glass

Fig. 9 Nano- and Micro-Laminates

Fig. 10 Hybrid Nano- and Micro-Laminated Materials

Fig. 11 Intermetallic/Metal Micro-Laminates Application

Fig. 12 AFOSR Polymeric Composite Degradation Program

Fig. 13 Interaction of Positrons with Polymers

- Preliminary data suggest that the static holes control the moisture diffusion below T_g
- Potential life-prediction tool
 - ⇒ design cure cycles with predicted durability
 - ⇒ residual life prediction / NDE

Fig. 14 Hole Effects on Controlling Moisture Diffusion

$$t = \frac{RT}{V_1} \left[\ln(1 - v_2) + v_2 + \chi v_2^2 + \frac{\rho V_1}{M_c} v_2 \lambda^2 \right]$$

- t = tensile stress
- R = gas constant
- T = temperature
- V₁ = molar volume of penetrant
- V₂ = volume fraction polymer
- χ = Flory-Higgins interaction parameter
- ρ = density of polymer
- M_c = effective molecular weight between cross-links
- λ = extension ratio

Experimental and Calculated Toluene Volume Fraction as a Function of Stress at 22°C

Fig. 15 Model for Sorption of Penetrant into Stressed Rubber (Treloar)

Fig. 17 Figure-of-Merit for TBC Design

Approach - grow CN_x pseudomorphically on template

- Grown on TiN (ZrN, HfN)

- » $\beta-C_3N_4$ (0001) = 0.644 nm
- » TiN (111) x2 = 0.60 nm (-7%)
- » ZrN (111) x2 = 0.651 (1.1%)
- » HfN (111) x2 = 0.645 (0.2%)

- Interfacial energy reduction
- Surface free energy
- Phase stability induced by stress
- Strain energy

Fig. 18 Crystalline Carbon Nitride Structural Template Method

- 100% crystalline CN_x/TiN
- Hardness about 60 GPa
- CN_x structure to be determined
- Smooth top surface

- Typical PVD coating, can be scaled-up readily
- Controlled wavelength (superlattice period)

Fig. 19 Nanolayer Stabilized Crystalline Carbon Nitride

Fig. 20(a) UF-HM Fiber Performance

Fig. 20(b) SEM micrographs which show that Nicalon[®] fibers are extensively degraded after heat treatment at 1600°C (top), while UF-HM fibers are not degraded at all after heat treatment at 1800°C (bottom).

(a) before

and

(b) after fiber pushout tests of a SCS-0 fiber / MgSiO_3 / ZrSiO_4 matrix composite hipped at 1450°C for 1 hour. The interface is weakened by the transformation and fibers can be pushout.

Fig. 21 Transformation Weakening of Interfaces

Fig. 22 Material Design Curves Debonding Mode

$$G = \frac{r_f (\phi_f \sigma_f^2 + \phi_m \sigma_f \sigma_m + \phi_m \sigma_m^2) \cdot 10^4}{\pi E_m (\ell/r_f)}$$

Fig. 23 Material Design Curves (Fiber Penetration Mode)

Fig. 24 Materials - Mechanics Fundamentals for Composite Materials

• Conservation Laws in Material Space - Failure Criteria

• Thermoelastic Medium

$$\int_{\partial\Omega} [u_i^k \sigma^{kj} n^j - W^e n^i + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\beta^2}{\lambda + \mu} \theta^2 n^i - \frac{\mu\beta}{\lambda + \mu} (\theta u_j^i n^j - u^i \theta_j n^j)] dl = 0 ,$$

• Viscoelastic Medium

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{2E} \right) = \sigma_{ij} - \eta \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}$$

• Non-Homogeneous Medium

$$J_{non-h} = \int_{\Gamma} [(W n^i - t^i u_j^i) + m(W x^k n^k - t^i u_{,k}^i x^k - \alpha u^k t^k / 2)] dl = 0$$

$$J_h = \int_{\Gamma} (W n^i - t^i u_j^i) dl = 0$$

$$M_h = \int_{\Gamma} (W n^k - t^i u_{,k}^i) x^k dl = 0$$

Fig. 25 Conservation Laws of Dissipative Systems

Problem:

Calculation of atomic bonding as a function of alloy composition

Approach:

Use technique based on the Fully Linearized Muffin-Tin Orbital method to calculate d-d Ti bonding in TiAl as a function of alloy content

Fig. 26 Atomic Bonding in TiAl